

1 **Statistical concerns and comments on “Evenly Distributed Protein Intake over 3**
2 **Meals Augments Resistance Exercise–Induced Muscle Hypertrophy in Healthy**
3 **Young Men”**

4 Igor Eckert¹

5 ¹ Undergraduate Program in Nutrition Sciences, Federal University of Health Sciences of
6 Porto Alegre (UFCSPA), Porto Alegre, Brazil.

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14 **Corresponding author details**

15 Full name: Igor Eckert

16 E-mail address: igoreckert2@gmail.com

17 Full postal address: Sarmiento Leite Street, 245, Centro Histórico, Porto Alegre, Rio
18 Grande do Sul, Brazil. Zip-code: 90050-170

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20 Dear Editor,

21 I have read with great interest the work done by Yasuda and colleagues (1), who
22 conducted a randomized clinical trial aimed to assess the effects of having an adequate
23 protein ingestion at breakfast, as compared to a skewed protein ingestion pattern, on
24 muscle mass accretion. Despite employing a sound methodology, the statistical analyses
25 performed by the authors may have produced misleading results. In this letter, I highlight
26 my main concerns and provide suggestions.

27 According to the article, the planned statistical analyses consisted of two different
28 hypothesis tests: a paired t test for within-group comparisons and an independent t test
29 for between-group differences. Such approach first calculates the pretreatment and post-
30 treatment difference for each group (also termed “changes in score”) and subsequently
31 compares changes in scores between groups. The results were reported as “the increases
32 in total lean soft tissue mass were greater in the high breakfast group (1.8 ± 0.3 kg) than
33 in the low breakfast group (2.5 ± 0.3 kg)”. However, the mean change from baseline
34 merely tells us that there is evidence of change over time but not whether this was a result
35 of the treatment itself. Alternatively, the ANCOVA is an extensively encouraged
36 statistical approach (2,3) that directly compares the post-treatment values between groups
37 while adjusting for relevant covariates.

38 Essentially, ANCOVA has two main advantages in clinical trials: first,
39 ascertainment of treatment effects between groups are more trustworthy. It adjusts each
40 subject’s follow-up measurement according to their baseline values, which is an effective
41 way of dealing with residual changes and correct for the phenomenon of regression to the
42 mean (4). In this study, the change between baseline and 12-week values may have been
43 related to the pretreatment values or to other unmeasured prognostic factors (e.g., physical
44 activity levels at baseline) by chance. Second, ANCOVA also maximizes statistical

45 power in randomized studies given pretreatment and post-treatment values have the same
46 within-group variance - which is assumed to be the case in randomized trials (4). This is
47 especially important in small studies that might lack power to detect statistically
48 significant results, an issue discussed by the authors in the article.

49 Although randomization is thought to ensure treatment groups are similar at
50 baseline, in small sample sizes we still may see dissimilarities with regards to known and
51 unknown prognostic factors. Hypothesis tests for baseline values may show no
52 statistically significant differences between groups; however, this approach is
53 conceptually illogical and discouraged by the CONSORT Statement (5,6). Moreover, the
54 decision to adjust for covariates should not depend on whether baseline differences are
55 statistically significant, but rather on variables known to affect the outcome measures (7).

56 Another concern of the composite-testing approach is related to the potential for
57 spurious findings due to multiplicity of tests. For each outcome, the composite procedure
58 of testing both groups against baseline and subsequently testing the changes in score
59 between groups equals to a false-positive rate of 14.26%. This issue is further amplified
60 because this approach was employed across all twelve outcomes: considering $\alpha=5\%$ and
61 $\beta=20\%$, the probability of at least one false-positive result in this study is therefore equal
62 to $1 - (1 - 0.05)^{36} \times 100 = 84.22\%$, following Boole's inequality from probability theory
63 - a much higher probability than the usually acceptable 5%.

64 It should be noted that these issues do not invalidate this study or its findings;
65 rather, I provide rationale and suggestions for adequate statistical inferences. In
66 conclusion, the comparison of two groups should be performed directly by 2-sample
67 methods to avoid misleading results from separate tests, and baseline measurements as
68 well as plausible prognostic factors should be used in ANCOVA. I hope the summarized

69 concerns are taken into consideration by the authors, peer-reviewers and investigators in
70 future research.

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87